

A Review of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy for Students of Color in Mathematics

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Article Info	Abstract
<p><i>Article History</i></p> <p>Received: April 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Mathematics, Students, Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5013858</p>	<p><i>In mathematics, there is a significant body of literature that explicates how Students of Color have consistently underperform relative to their White counterparts. There is a need to understand how the performance disparities emerged and what instructional method could assist Students of Color in mathematics learning. This review particularly examines how the prevalence of Whiteness in mathematics education can create educational barriers for Students of Color and how culturally relevant pedagogy can reduce those barriers. The review begins by examining Whiteness and its resulting barriers for Students of Color in mathematics. Then the review examines the potential of culturally relevant pedagogy to address the educational barriers. Whiteness and its Resulting Barriers for Students of Color in Mathematics.</i></p>

INTRODUCTION

This section uses Whiteness to critique mathematics education and how Students of Color are affected by it. “Whiteness can be defined as a system of privilege based on race whereby White ideology is viewed as a reference point from which all other identities are compared” (Fine, Weis, & Pruitt, 2004, p.856). Thus, identities such as Native American, Latinx, and Black are perceived as society’s multicultural subcultures in the presence of Whiteness. Leonardo (2009) elaborates that “Whiteness is not a culture but a social concept” (Leonardo, 2009, p. 170). This does not imply that White people do not have a culture. Ice hockey, ballet, hamburgers, and fries are examples of White cultural practices that even non-White people partake in, though such practices are not indigenous to them. Leonardo (2009) continues that Whiteness is often invisible but more recognizable by people of color. For example, people of color easily recognized and protested the Caucasian color of band-aids, however, Whites may have assumed that color to be standard. It is within such standardizations that Whiteness uses a “colorblind” consciousness to suppress the discourse on race, and therefore normalize White experiences (Bonilla-Silva, 2003; Fine, Weis, & Pruitt, 2004). By not acknowledging race, the colorblind perspective un/intentionally undermines students’ unique experiences across race lines. Just like the protest “All Lives Matter” undermines “Black Lives Matter” (Carney, 2016), the perpetuation of cultural neutrality/color-blindness undermines the call for multicultural education. To be specific, one cannot claim “it is not about color” when people of color are mostly affected.

Furthermore, White students’ supremacy in educational achievement can be viewed as a subset of Whiteness, where racial hierarchies are legitimized. For instance, reports in America on mathematics achievement show Asian American students outscoring White students, however, society refrains from pathologizing White’s underachievement (Martin, 2009). However, when White students outperform Students of Color, then Whiteness or the colorblind racial ideology would support explanations for presenting the performance as “gaps”. It is important to understand the role that Whiteness plays in mathematics learning experiences for Students of Color, especially as White methods of knowing are viewed as natural and they dominate other’s ways of knowing. Specifically, how does Whiteness influence the interactions, expectations, and kinds of experiences that teachers and students have in mathematics? The discussion examines the connection of Whiteness to deficit perspectives, to mathematics curriculum, and to teacher education.

Whiteness and the Occurrence of Deficit Perspectives

Battey and Leyva (2016) contend that colorblind ideologies and practices relegate Students of Color and limit their positive development of racial and mathematics identities. By perceiving Students of Color as incapable, Whites end up receiving unquestionable legitimacy in educational spaces (Moore, 2008). In mathematics education, notions of incapability are observed in racialized hierarchies of mathematical ability that position Students of Color at the bottom and cause them to question their identities as doers of mathematics. Such deficit perspectives are associated with disidentification with mathematics, lower-quality instructional experiences, and poor relationships with teachers (Oppland-Cordell, 2014; Spencer, 2009). Tracking, referral to

remedial/developmental programs, and labelling students as “at risk” are living examples of racialized hierarchies of mathematical ability that frame students’ identities (Lewis, 2004). Tracking, particularly, is ineffective (Burris & Welner, 2005) and Students of Color are highly populated in the lower tracks, while the higher tracks are mostly composed of White students (Chambers, Huggins, Locke, & Fowler, 2014; Tyson, 2011). One could argue that segregation is at play and the worst part is that it appears as standard/normal. Rather than tracking, many scholars have investigated the academic effects of detracking and found it to significantly improve mathematics performance for Students of Color (e.g., Condrón, Tope, Steidl, & Freeman, 2013). This is especially true when detracking is combined with academic support such as after school classes (Condrón, Tope, Steidl, & Freeman, 2013).

Another manifestation of deficit perspectives is teachers holding low expectations of Students of Color (e.g., Pringle, Lyons, & Booker, 2010). Such teachers often blame racial minorities’ families and communities for low academic performance (Lynn, Bacon, Totten, Bridges, & Jennings, 2010). Teachers can send overt messages by commenting that a particular group of students requires “basics” (Battey & Franke, 2015). Overt messages of low expectations can also be sent to high performing Students of Color. Battey and Levy (2016) provide an example that a high performing Black student attending a calculus course can be questioned by a White peer whether they are at the right place. Students internalize these messages to form their mathematical identities. Several studies show that holding high expectations in Students of Color has been documented to improve performance (e.g., Corbett, Williams, & Wilson, 2005; Gollnick & Chinn, 2009; Johnson, 2009; Moses-Snipes & Snipes 2005). Blanchard and Muller (2015) explain that “...teachers’ perceptions of hard work help nearly all students to get ahead and on to more demanding math classes” (p. 273). Whether it is tracking or low expectations, the colorblind ideology, which is embraced by Whiteness, constructs the meaning of being “good” in mathematics and positions students across a continuum of mathematics ability.

The mathematical delegitimization of Students of Color also puts them in a position to prove themselves (McGee & Martin, 2011). McGee and Martin (2011) calls this stereotype management and their analysis found that high performing Black engineering and mathematics students were always mindful that their racial identities were undervalued. The students in their study shifted from proving stereotypes wrong to an internal motivation to attain academic success in White spaces. However, the risk Students of Color face in confirming their assigned relegated position is often referred to as stereotype threat (Steele, 1997). Steele (1997) identified racial *stereotype threat* as a factor that can widen performance disparities between Students of Color and their White counterparts. This is also witnessed in mathematics (e.g., Tine & Gotlieb, 2013), but by validating students’ cultural identities, the psychological threat from being negatively stereotyped is often reduced (Cohen, Garcia, Purdie-Vaughns, Apfel, & Brzustoski, 2009).

Whiteness in Mathematics Curriculum

Historically, People of Color were barred from participating in White America’s educational system, for example, *Plessy v. Ferguson* (1896). To connect history with Whiteness ideologies, “one can examine curricula for presentations of mathematics as neutral or cultureless as well” (Battey & Levy, 2016, p.66). Bourdieu (2003) argued that a White/Eurocentric curriculum had done “double violence”: (1) one culture was imposed on others; (2) the imposition was forgotten. In relation to mathematics, others’ culture in mathematizing was subjugated by White mathematical thinking. Then educational institutions inherited the White mathematics and naturalized it to a point many believe it is the only knowledge worth including in school mathematics curricula. Some scholars argue that even Students of Color believe that the creation and ownership of mathematics belongs to a community other than their own (Barta, Cuch, & Exton, 2012).

This belief, and Students of Color’s experiences in mathematics, has been used to explain the racial disparities in mathematics achievement (Barta, Eglash, & Barkley, 2014). With the domination of Whiteness in mathematics curricula, Students of Color often feel either hypervisible (Higginbotham, 2001) or invisible (Feagin & Sikes, 1994). They feel hypervisible because their population is so low in quantitative subjects, and invisible because their culture, interests, and history are not acknowledged. Hypervisibility in Students of Color may bring about essentialism, tokenism, and the pressure of one student representing the whole race (Moore, 2008). In mathematics classrooms, hypervisibility of Students of Color would trigger teachers to focus on the students’ behavior while their mathematical thinking continues to be invisible. “Examining both the invisibility and hypervisibility of Students of Color in mathematics spaces with respect to being successful in higher-tracked mathematics courses, for example, shows whiteness systemically acting within educational institutions” (Battey & Levy, 2016, p.73).

The Role of Teacher Education in Perpetuating Whiteness

Milner, Pearman, and McGee (2013) noted that “the curriculum of teacher education mirrors, in many ways, the P-12 curriculum in that it is Eurocentric and White dominated” (p. 158). In fact, Siwatu (2011) discovered that preservice teachers felt more equipped to teach in suburban schools than in urban schools. He rationalized that a “universal” approach (culturally neutral approach) used in teacher education contributes to preservice teachers’ lack of preparedness for urban schools. Whiteness is present in this universal approach because it only develops competent and confident teachers for suburban schools which are “Whiter” in culture

and populace (Simon & Johnson, 2015). Siwatu (2011) continues that because of the universal approach being extensively used in America, many preservice teachers may not be getting mastery and experience in culturally and linguistically diverse educational settings. For these reasons, traditionally trained teachers find it difficult to connect with their diverse students, which often leads to students participating less and teachers developing misconceptions of student ability, potential, and motivation (Hernandez et al., 2013). The problem is propagated with teacher education programs only requiring one multicultural education course for prospective teachers. Furthermore, a majority (78%) of teacher education faculty are White (Milner, Pearman, & McGee, 2013) and Sleeter (2016) explains that, less diversity in the teacher education faculty results in White interests being more represented in coursework than culturally diverse backgrounds.

Even when teachers gain experience in high racial minority schools, they frequently transfer to schools serving wealthier, “Whiter” student populations (Simon & Johnson, 2015). It is often the high-quality teachers that tend to leave, and this turnover has been increasing for more than two decades (Ronfeldt, Loeb, & Wyckoff, 2013). Teacher turnover is known to negatively affect mathematics performance in Students of Color (Ronfeldt et al., 2013). Simon and Johnson (2015) discuss a variety of reasons why mathematics teachers migrate to Whiter schools (e.g., better pay or working conditions). Among these reasons is that teacher education programs are not successfully equipping teachers for culturally and linguistically diverse students (Picower, 2009). Picower’s (2009) study (*The unexamined Whiteness of teaching: how White teachers maintain and enact dominant racial ideologies*) demonstrates how White teachers deny, subvert, or avoid multicultural education in order to maintain their hegemonic understandings. In multicultural education, this is often referred to as resistance. Picower (2009) elaborates that fear of people of color based on stereotypes, media representations, and cultural incongruence is one of the methods of resistance. The fear can escalate to terror when a White teacher is alone among people of color, like in a classroom. Picower (2009) quotes one White teacher describing a neighboring school with a high number of Black students:

We always knew that was the high school that was always in trouble. That was the high school that had really big Black football players... I mean my friends in general didn’t want to go to their school for sports events because it was a little scary. Scary like their attitude and stuff was different – seemed to be different than ours – and their behaviors and stuff seemed to be different [to] ours, so we avoided it... I think that you are always going to have those feelings (p. 202).

The perception of different as dangerous highlights that Whiteness is the standard to which safety is measured. In order to mitigate the fleeing of teachers from high racial minority schools, it is important to recruit more culturally and linguistically diverse teachers and embrace a multicultural approach rather than the universal/cultural neutral approach to preparing teachers (Picower, 2009; Sleeter, 2017). Otherwise, Students of Color will continue to have more teachers (than White students) that are novice, have a lateral entry license, have low licensure test scores, are certified but not in mathematics, are not board certified, have no graduate degree, and come from uncompetitive colleges (Clotfelter, Ladd, & Vigdor, 2010). However, “...having a teacher with strong rather than weak credentials would, on average, more than offset the adverse effect of racial and socio-economic differences...” (Clotfelter, Ladd, & Vigdor, 2010, p. 34).

Conclusion

The basic assumption here is that mathematics education is not neutral and that it aligns with society’s dominant racial ideologies. Using Whiteness as a frame for critiquing mathematics education suggests ways that Students of Color have been academically delegitimized. The delegitimization may cause Students of Color to develop the need to prove themselves, to experience stereotype threats, and to reject or disidentify with mathematics. These issues are known to negatively affect the mathematics performance of Students of Color and so, while hierarchies may be necessary, the virtue of a hierarchy of mathematical competence that is founded on such biases is questionable. That is, when Students of Color’s participation in mathematics is delegitimized, then their clumping at the bottom of these hierarchies is not a valid depiction of their mathematical ability and knowledge construction. Furthermore, the presence of biases will continue to ensure that hierarchies are part “... of larger racialization processes that, on the surface, appear to put forth objective findings but, based on more critical analysis, are designed to maintain racial hierarchies and socially construct African American, Latino, and Native American students as less” (Martin, 2009, p. 324).

Many solutions have been proposed to improve the learning experiences of Students of Color in White settings. For example, Egalite, Kisida, and Winters (2015) proposed Caucasian, Black, and Asian/Pacific Island students be taught by race-congruent mathematics teachers. It is true that Race-congruent teachers have positive effects on students’ performance (Egalite, Kisida, & Winters, 2015), but teachers of color can also perpetuate Whiteness (Battey & Levy, 2016). As part of the many solutions, this review of the literature supports two notions: 1) White students’ mathematics performance should not be viewed as a ceiling or standard for all to strive for; and, 2) Cultural diversity should be embraced in the teaching and learning of mathematics instead of relying on Eurocentric/White curricula. By doing so, then perhaps Students of Color’s performance can improve without establishing ceilings.

The Potential of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy to Address Educational Barriers

There are numerous methods of connecting mathematics to culture. For example, Barta, Eglash, and Barkley (2014) show the presence of mathematical concepts in cornrow hair braiding, Mayan culture, the streets of Ouro Preto (Brazil), Navajo beading and weaving patterns, Adinkra symbols, the game of Klappenspiel, graffiti shapes and styles, stick charts and woven fronds, Rangolee and Kolam folk art designs, and the Potawatomi two-sided dice. When culture is present in mathematics it demonstrates to learners that mathematics is not an isolated subject. Additionally, learners may begin to appreciate how mathematics influences culture and how culture can dictate the creation and use of mathematics. Regrettably, the infusion of culture in college mathematics is among the least practiced (Rodriguez, 2015) and the least studied areas of research (Brown, Boda, Lemmi, & Monroe, 2018). This paper concurs with Sleeter's (2012) argument that the use of culture in education should be accompanied by evidenced-based assessments of academic impact and research explaining its positive affective impact. This section presents what has been studied about CRP and it begins by discussing its definitions and constructs, effectiveness of CRP, and why CRP is not generally implemented in mathematics education.

Definitions and Constructs of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy

The term CRP is based in the constructivist paradigm and ontological foundation. Hatch (2002) argues that the constructivist ontology describes knowledge as individualized and founded upon unique perspectives and constructions of diversity, difference, and culture. Howell (2013) expounds that CRP dictates that educators must acknowledge that teaching and learning is socially and culturally constructed and inherently value laden. Additionally, CRP uses the Racial Identity Theory, Critical Theory, and Social Cognitive Theory. These theories together with the constructivist paradigm create the basis to which CRP is established and can be implemented by educators in mathematics (Martin, 2016). It is Ladson-Billings (1995) that coined the phrase "culturally relevant pedagogy" (CRP) and popularized it in her article "Toward a Theory of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy". However, CRP has also been referred to as "Culturally Compatible" (Jacob & Jordan, 1987), "Culturally Congruent" (Au & Kawakami, 1994) and "Culturally Responsive" (Gay, 2010).

Ladson-Billings (1995) describes CRP as a "pedagogy of opposition...committed to collective, not merely individual empowerment" (p. 160). Gay (2010) explains CRP as teaching "to and through [students'] personal and cultural strengths, their intellectual capabilities, and their prior accomplishments" (p. 26); CRP is based on "close interactions among ethnic identity, cultural background, and student achievement" (p. 27). Gay (2010) continues that, "Students of Color come to school having already mastered many cultural skills and ways of knowing. To the extent that when teaching builds on these capabilities, academic success will result" (p. 213). More recently, Paris (2012) proposed the phrase "culturally sustaining pedagogy" (CSP) and claimed it to be a better phrase than the previous ones. Paris (2012) argues that the phrase CSP ensures "the valuing and maintenance of our increasingly multiethnic and multilingual society" (p. 94).

Beyond different phrases, researchers also disagree on how to define CRP. According to Ladson-Billings' conception of CRP, three criteria must be satisfied: (1) there must be academic success; (2) cultural competence must be developed and preserved, and (3) there must be a critical conscious development through which the current social order can be challenged by students (Ladson-Billings, 1994). The usage of the phrase CRP is also seen in Brown-Jeffy and Cooper (2011) who leveraged the work of Gay (1994, 2000), Nieto (1990), and Ladson-Billings' (1994) to develop five principles for CRP: "(1) identity and achievement, (2) equity and excellence, (3) developmental awareness, (4) teaching the whole child, and (5) student-teacher relationships" (p. 71). There are many variations, but these principles highly overlap in meaning. In fact, most scholars agree that CRP is a mindful practice and research-based instructional method that promotes students' racial and cultural identities.

This paper uses the phrase CRP over others because it is the most commonly used one and it has been reinterpreted to become broader than how Gloria Ladson-Billings first envisioned it (Brown-Jeffy & Cooper, 2011; Henry, 2017). That said, there are recent studies (e.g., Brown, Boda, Lemmi, & Monroe, 2018) that still use Ladson-Billings' original version of CRP and its accompanying theory to understand how students' cultural references can be incorporated in pedagogy. The next section also uses theoretical underpinnings of CRP by Ladson-Billings (1992, 2014) to explain three foundational constructs behind CRP. The three constructs are: conception of self and others, conceptions of knowledge, and social relations.

Conception of Self and Others. Ladson-Billings (1992, 2014) summarizes that culturally relevant teachers: believe that all students can thrive academically, perceive teaching as an art that is unpredictable and ever evolving, perceive themselves as participants of the community, perceive teaching as contributing back to that community, and subscribe to the Freirean idea of teaching as mining. Believing in students' success or holding high expectations for all students is frequently mentioned in CRP studies (e.g., Bonner, 2014). Gay (2010) refers to it as a pedagogy that insists "on high quality performance" (p. 217). To achieve this, some suggest adopting a warm demander pedagogy - "provide a tough-minded, no-nonsense, structured, and disciplined classroom environment for kids whom society had psychologically and physically abandoned" (Irvine & Fraser, 1998, p. 56). Similar to Ladson-Billings (1992), Bonner (2014) explains that students need to

feel like they can construct, discover, and engage with mathematics. This involves the instructor being willing to give up some power, otherwise, knowledge will simply be transmitted from the instructor. Bonner (2014) explains that underserved students, such as Students of Color, “often feel disempowered in the mathematics classroom, largely because of prior experiences” (p. 392). In her observation of culturally relevant classrooms “it was difficult to determine who was driving the lessons (students or teacher) at any point in time” (Bonner, 2014, p. 393).

Social Relations. Culturally relevant teachers: support fluid student-teacher relationships, establish a connectedness with all of the students, inspire students to learn collaboratively, establish a community of learners, and incite learners to be responsible for another. Establishing camaraderie between all those involved in the learning process is a key feature of CRP (Hernandez, Morales, & Shroyer, 2013). Wang (2007) and Gay (2010) propose that this can be done by building teamwork into the curriculum and setting clear guidelines of how to make it successful. Ukpokodu (2011) suggests using heterogeneous groupings based on race, gender, ability, language, etc. Ukpokodu (2011) also suggests infusing democratic values in group work and creating complex tasks with multiple parts to allow each group member’s contribution. There must be trust, social networks, and an environment of open exchange, which instructors can establish by serving as facilitators and repositioning themselves as equal to students (Wang, 2007). Gay (2010) explains that “students perform much better in environments where they feel comfortable and valued” (p.232). She continues that such environments can be created by the instructor positioning herself as a “friend, mentor, model, critic, teacher, and confidante” (p. 218) to her college students. Fostering such relationships with students and supporting their critical consciousness assists with intellectual empowerment (Timmons-Brown & Warner, 2016).

Conception of Knowledge. Culturally relevant teachers believe: “knowledge is not static; it is shared, recycled, and constructed; knowledge must be viewed critically, teachers must be passionate about knowledge and learning; teachers must scaffold, or build bridges, to facilitate learning; and assessment must be multifaceted, incorporating multiple forms of excellence” (Ladson-Billings, 1995, p.481). Many studies show that domain-general learning is facilitated by language, culture, and other socially constructed factors (e.g., Boykin & Allen, 2004; Delpit, 1995; Gay, 2010; Ladson-Billings, 1994, 2001; Nieto, 2012). This includes domain-specific fields, such as mathematics. For instance, Ukpokodu (2011) argues that teachers must realize that mathematical knowledge rests within a group’s sociocultural frame. Thus, it is important to allow students to express their mathematical knowledge in their unique ways especially when these ways can be based on culture. For example, long division in Brazil is performed differently than in the US, and so a Brazilian student should not have to give up such mathematical strategies in order to assimilate in a US mathematics classroom. Also, teachers should be able to build on what their students already know as they support them to be critical independent thinkers (Hernandez, Morales, & Shroyer, 2013). When teachers contextualize mathematics based on students’ interests, experiences, and communities then the subject can be used as a tool to critique the social order (Martin, Gholson, & Leonard, 2010). This perception also establishes goals for mathematics education that embrace not only high performance for students but also having them use mathematics to develop their identities and to amend the conditions of their lives in emancipatory ways (e.g., Gutstein, 2006). When teachers contextualize mathematics and then scaffold instruction, positive inclusive learning spaces can be created (Klinger & Gonzalez, 2009; Worrell, 2007).

Models of CRP in Mathematics

Though the praxis of CRP in mathematics is minimal, there are varying CRP models that are specific to mathematics. With different models, it implies instructors’ use of CRP can also differ (Brown-Jeffy & Cooper, 2011). The two most common models are Culturally Relevant Mathematics Pedagogy (CureMap; Rubel & Chu, 2011) and Culturally Responsive Mathematics Teaching (CRMT; Bonner & Adams, 2012). Table 1 shows the principles of these models. In short, CureMap promotes conceptual understanding and critical consciousness by leveraging student’s experiences. CRMT focuses on student-teacher communication, teacher knowledge, and student-teacher relationships and trust as foundations to student learning and academic success. Hernandez, Morales, and Shroyer (2013) also produced a Culturally Responsive Science and Mathematics Teaching (CRSMT) model. The CRSMT model considers dispositions and instructional techniques that educators can execute to teach mathematics in a culturally responsive manner. The CRSMT model can also be used as an assessment tool for analyzing mathematics instruction and its cultural responsiveness. Consequently, the CRSMT model can be used by educators to assess and reflect on their teaching practices. Hernandez et al.’s (2013) CRSMT model is governed by five principles: content integration, facilitating knowledge construction, prejudice reduction, social justice, and academic development. (Appendix I shows this model.)

Table 1

Models of CRP in Mathematics

Model	Citation	Principles of the Model
Culturally Relevant Mathematics Pedagogy (CureMap)	Rubel and Chu (2011)	Teaching Mathematics for Understanding Center Instruction on Students’ Experiences

Model	Citation	Principles of the Model
		Develop Students' Critical Consciousness with or about mathematics
Culturally Responsive Science and Mathematics Teaching (CRSMT)	Hernandez, Morales, and Shroyer (2013)	Content Integration Facilitating Knowledge Construction Prejudice Reduction Social Justice Academic Development
Culturally Responsive Mathematics Teaching (CRMT)	Bonner and Adams (2012)	Communication Knowledge Trust/Relationships Constant Reflection/Revision

This review of the CRP literature preferred Hernandez et al.'s (2013) CRSMT model when designing mathematics learning modules. The CRSMT model is more comprehensive than other models and it has more clarity and specificity for operationalizing CRP in mathematics. Unlike other models, the CRSMT model adds a prejudice reduction principle and it prescribes "...methods for candidates to use in dealing with injustices when they encounter them in the schools" (Hernandez et al., 2013, p.818). Clarity in prejudice reduction is important because stereotype threats, microaggressions, and other injustices in classrooms have been shown to influence students' performance (e.g., Alfaro et al., 2009). However, prejudice reduction in the CRSMT model focuses only on native language support, fostering positive student-to-student interactions, and creating a safe learning environment. This paper recognizes that prejudice reduction is more complex than the one proposed by the CRSMT model, but it is a good introduction for discussing the occurrence of injustices in the classroom.

Social justice is another a key element that is often found in scholars' conceptions of CRP. However, Hernandez et al.'s (2013) observation of teachers who use CRP shows that it is "a challenge to find evidence of dispositions or behaviors related to social justice" (p.815). Social justice is defined as educators' willingness "to act as agents of change" (Villegas and Lucas 2002, p.5), by emboldening their students to challenge the status quo which then supports "the development of sociopolitical or critical consciousness" (Ladson-Billings, 1995, p.483). One could argue that the purpose of school is to impart knowledge, develop critical consciousness among students, and nurture students to be agents of change themselves. Another could argue that the purpose of school is to preserve the status quo. This paper certainly subscribes to the former notion.

Effectiveness of CRP

The infusion of cultural references in mathematics provides teachers with opportunities to socially, politically, culturally, and academically improve mathematics curriculum for students while assisting educators in addressing various student needs (Sampson & Garrison-Wade, 2010). Particularly, CRP was proposed to address the academic underachievement of underprivileged students and Students of Color such as African Americans, Latinxs, and Native Americans (Alismail, 2016; Bonner & Adams, 2012). Some studies, though few, show that CRP can successfully be implemented in mathematics classrooms (e.g., Aguirre, & del Rosario Zavala, 2013; Brown-Jeffy, 2009; Hernandez et al. 2013; Jackson, 2013; Leonard & Moore, 2014). Beyond implementation, there is evidence showing how the guidelines of CRP can promote academic engagement and achievement (e.g., Christianakis, 2011; Byrd, 2016; Dickson, Chun, & Fernandez, 2016; Rodriguez, Jones, Pang, & Park, 2004; Sleeter, 2012; Tate, 1995). Rubel and Chu (2011) demonstrated that their CureMap model provided students with broader and richer opportunities to learn mathematics. This was especially true with higher-level cognitive demand tasks, which facilitated deep engagement with mathematics and allowed students to detect patterns across mathematics representations.

Bonner and Adams' (2013) study reported that CRP inspires vibrant classroom discussions that uphold students' cultural integrity. The dynamic interactions they observed in their study contributed to students' mathematics success. Similar effects were seen in research by Jackson (2013) where healthy student-teacher relational interactions were key in mediating students' mathematics success. Jackson (2013) identified teachers' understanding of cultural competence, culturally relevant pedagogy, and critical consciousness as contributors to students' mathematics success. There are more studies that also confirm that CRP encourages a sense of critical consciousness (e.g., Epstein, Mayorga, & Nelson, 2011; Martell, 2013; Morrell & Duncan-Andrade, 2002; Stovall, 2006) among students.

Other benefits students often acquire from CRP exposure are positive racial/ethnic identity affirmation and positive attitudes towards others (e.g., Aldana, Rowley, Checkoway, & Richards-Schuster, 2012; Dessel, Rogge, & Garlington, 2006). This is also true in mathematics, where Waddell's (2014) CRP mathematics educators elaborated that CRP assisted students to preserve their cultural integrity as they aimed to attain academic excellence. When considering students' perspectives, Hubert (2014) found that students mostly had

positive attitudes toward the use of CRP in mathematics. In fact, all of the students in the study preferred CRP over traditional methods of instruction. The students also indicated that CRP assisted to increase their interest in mathematics. Lastly, Byrd (2016) found that CRP is “an important method for promoting achievement and positive identities for students of all races” (p.7). This is a significant result because of a common misconception that CRP only caters to one group and thus positive effects are unique to that group.

Why CRP is Not Implemented in Mathematics

There are several reasons why CRP is not generally implemented in mathematics courses. Among these reasons is the cultural incongruity between educators and students (Ramsay-Jordan, 2017). When there is a misalignment between teachers’ and students’ culture, this often leads many teachers to rely on textbooks and preparation methods geared for standardized tests (Ramsay-Jordan, 2017). Irvine (2010) elaborates that lack of CRP knowledge causes many educators to avoid it and often resort to adopting slang speech, incorporating popular culture into the curriculum, or simply acknowledging ethnic holidays. Irvine (2010) continues that such practices are ineffective and may jeopardize the student-teacher relationships that are so important to successful implementation of CRP.

Wager (2012) states that educators’ struggle to connect the mathematics students witness in school to the mathematics students practice out of school is another reason why they do not use CRP. Contextualizing mathematics to have real-world applications can be difficult, especially when the real-world applications are dependent on students’ culture and interests. In fact, many educators believe that mathematics is culturally neutral. Leonard and Moore (2014) interviewed preservice teachers who showed reluctance to use CRP. The preservice teachers believed “math is math” (p.82) and failed to understand “what culture had to do with mathematics” (p.82). Similar sentiments appeared in Siwatu’s (2011) study and he went further to identify teacher attitudes toward student diversity as another barrier to using CRP in mathematics. These attitudes can manifest with Students of Color being invisible to teachers, receiving low-expectations from teachers, and other deficit views (Ramirez, Gonzales-Galindo, & Roy, 2016).

Unlike teacher attitudes and racism, teachers can have biases that could constrain them from using CRP in mathematics. Biases refer to preferences and impartial judgement coming from prejudice (Jackson, Appelgate, Seiler, Sheth, & Nadolny, 2016). Specifically, many educators prefer to avoid controversial topics such as discussions based on race or ethnicity (Simic-Muller, Fernandes, & Felton-Koestler, 2015). These educators find such discussions to be uncomfortable and so they find refuge in a color-blind approach to teaching mathematics. Color-blindness equates to neutrality, and to wash one’s hands in the struggle to include others’ cultural references in education means to side with a “White curriculum”. Such teachers are portraying personal biases, but there are also structural biases (Buchanan, 2016) that would limit implementation of CRP in mathematics classrooms. Structural biases can be university policies, culture, learning materials, and teacher practices. For example, textbooks are frequently culturally biased. That is, they do not show evidence of inclusion and equity (Bright, 2016; Oliver & Oliver, 2013). Instead, current mathematics curriculum, including textbooks, are deeply established in cultural experiences largely synonymous with America’s White middle-class (Bright, 2016; Oliver & Oliver, 2013). Lastly, School Reform Models are also known to constrain educators from using CRP in mathematics classrooms. Reforms that support standardization and accountability often cause teachers to only satisfy the standards and prepare students for high-stakes tests (Ukpokodu, 2011). Infusion of cultural references in such instructional methods is rarely considered (Ukpokodu, 2011).

Conclusion on CRP

The reviewed literature showed a mixture of challenges and successes for educators who seek to implement CRP in mathematics. The consistently changing demographics and diverse settings on campuses indicate the growing need for educators to incorporate sociocultural factors and perceptions that positively affect interactions happening in classrooms (Wallace & Brand, 2012). However, the implementation of CRP in mathematics is limited and under studied (Bonner, 2014). Scholars state the implementation constraints are due to lack of CRP knowledge and models, cultural incongruity, perceptions of mathematics as culturally neutral, teacher attitudes towards students of color, personal and structural biases, and school reform models (Bonner, 2014; Gay, 2010; Ramsay-Jordan, 2017; Ukpokodu, 2011). The development of mathematics CRP models is highly encouraged (e.g., Brandt & Chernoff, 2015), especially in college undergraduate mathematics courses (e.g., Brown, Boda, Lemmi, & Monroe, 2018; Jett, 2013) where the researcher found no studies on the effectiveness of CRP.

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